

WA LUCAP Lung Cancer Interim Report Feb 2025

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The Patient Journey

All co-ordinated through respiratory teams

Coordination:
Radiology
Pathology
Theatres / G75
Anaesthetics
Lung function
Nuclear Med

Respiratory

- CNC / Fellow / Cons
- Fast track clinics

Nodule MDM
PFTs
PET

Bronchoscopy (EBUS)

CT-FNA

Cancer MDM

Referrals:

- CTS
- Med Onc
- Rad Onc
- Palliative

Initial referral

First appointment

First procedure

First diagnosis

First treatment

WA Lung Cancer services are increasingly stretched

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- Lung cancer incidence will increase for next 20 years
- Increase in complexity for diagnosis, staging and personalised treatment
 - EBUS bronchoscopy
 - Tissue for genetic mutation analysis
 - Neoadjuvant treatment – new paradigm in 2024
 - Navigation bronchoscopy
- Private services are unlikely to be able to provide this level of complexity

National Lung Cancer Screening Program

The new NLCSP is a screening program using low-dose computed tomography scans to look for lung cancer in high-risk people without any symptoms. It aims to find lung cancer early and reduce deaths from lung cancer. Screening services will begin for eligible people from July 2025.

Roll out: 01 July 2025

30% uptake in WA = ~31,000 individuals screened / yr

Projected: ~880 new referrals
 ~430 new cases of lung cancer

Timeliness of care - Optimal Care Pathway targets

(Cancer Australia, 1st published 2014)

Optimal care pathway for people with lung cancer
SECOND EDITION

LUCAP data

Lung Cancer Clinical Quality Data Platform

- Prospective data since Sept 2022
- Now 4 WA sites (SCGH, FSH, RPH, SJOGMid)
- Benchmarking against OCP CQI targets (and others)
- >1,200 cases

- Data on next 3 slides: Sept 2023 – Sept 2024 (with 3 months follow up)
- Focus only on OCP timeliness reporting
- More comprehensive reporting to follow

Time from initial referral to first appointment

Overall, 50% of patients were seen within **14 days**; median wait of 16 days

Sir Charles Gairdner Hospital
Median 20 days

Fiona Stanley Hospital
Median 15 days

Royal Perth Hospital
Median 7 days

St John of God Midland Public
& Private Hospital
Median 11 days

Time from initial referral to first diagnostic procedure

Overall, **54%** of participants underwent their first diagnostic procedure within **28 days**; median time of 30 days

Sir Charles Gairdner Hospital
Median 24 days

Fiona Stanley Hospital
Median 28 days

Royal Perth Hospital
Median 27 days

St John of God Midland Public
& Private Hospital
Median 20 days

Time from initial referral to first treatment

Overall, 17% of patients commenced treatment within **42 days**; median time of 76 days

Sir Charles Gairdner Hospital
Median 76 days

Fiona Stanley Hospital
Median 78 days

Royal Perth Hospital
Median 84 days

St John of God Midland Public
& Private Hospital
Median 63 days

OCP timepoints – a system wide failure

	TARGET	SCGH (n=138)	FSH (n=132)	RPH (n=123)	All
Ref to FSA (median days)		20	15	7	20
% meeting 14 day target	>80%	24/80 (30%)	37/86 (43%)	63/97 (65%)	167/331 (50%)
Ref to first procedure (median days)		24	28	27	30
% meeting 28 day target	>90%	54/97 (56%)	55/111 (50%)	55/103 (53%)	207/381 (54%)
Ref to first Dx (median days)		35	41	42	39
% meeting 28 day target		36/107 (34%)	35/117 (30%)	41/105 (39%)	152/415 (37%)
Ref to first Rx (median days)		76	78	84	80
% meeting 42 day target	>60%	12/102 (12%)	13/106 (12%)	16/97 (17%)	64/382 (17%)

FSA = first specialist appointment
 Dx = diagnosis
 Rx = treatment

What patients say:

“Hideous time of waiting”

“Immense anxiety”

“I was scared, really scared”

WA data - Change over time

OCP 14-day target (aim >80%)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
NMHS	54%	55%	53%	30%	30%
SMHS	60%	49%	52%	30%	43%
EMHS					
RPH	46%	65%	38%	74%	65%
SJOG Mid	72%	86%	78%	58%	63%

LUCAP = 12 months prospective data collection; previous data were retrospective over 3 months

How does WA compare?

	NSW EnRICH	NT*	TAS*	VLCR	LUCAP Qld**	LUCAP WA
OCP 14d (>80%)			93%		43%	50%
OCP 28d (>90%)	57%	21d median	71%	70.4%	61%	37%
OCP 42d (>60%)	21%	60 d median		48.1%	75%	16%

Note: Different data sources, with exception of LUCAP WA and LUCAP Qld;

VLCR = Victorian Lung Cancer Registry

*Retrospective audit data

**low numbers (collaboration only from Nov 24)

[CINSW EnRICH](#)
[Victorian Lung Cancer Registry](#)

Summary

- Data demonstrate a system wide failure of lung cancer services across WA health
- Implementation of the NLCSP will exacerbate these failings
- Changes, efficiencies and innovations are urgently required

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